

Factors Influencing Armed Banditry in Kebbi State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Banditry is one of the major forms of insecurity that affected Kebbi State for the past decade. Banditry has affected all facets of human life among which is food security in the state affected. The objective of the article is to explain the impact of banditry on food security and highlight the recent effort of the government in tackling banditry to improve food security among others. The methodology to be adopted to generate data for the study is through the use of focus group discussion, questionnaire, and in depth interview of persons by bandits which are sampled for the study. The study will adopt both Qualitative and quantitative methods of Data analyses. Finally, it will conclude that armed banditry is a menace prevalent across the state, which needs to be addressed. It will equally proffer solutions for curtailing armed banditry in Kebbi state, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Banditry

Banditry is a type of organized crime committed by outlaws typically involving the threat or use of violence. A person who engages in banditry is known as bandit and primarily commits crimes such as extortion, rape, robbery, and murder, either as an individual or in groups. Banditry is a vague concept of criminality and in modern usage can be synonymous for gangsterism, brigandage, marauding, and thievery. The term bandit (introduced to English via Italian around 1590) originates with the early Germanic legal practice of outlawing criminals, termed “*bannan* (English ban). The legal term in the Holy Roman Empire was *Acht* or *Reichsacht*, translated as “Imperial ban”. In modern Italian the equivalent word “bandito” literally means banned or a banned or a banned person.

According to Adedeji (2021) he views that for some time now, Nigeria has been a hotbed of conflicts. Apart from the perennial conflict between the farmers and herdsmen, there are other notable security challenges, which include the activities of the Biafra separatists, militants(IPOB) Boko Haram in the North-East, Kidnappings in many parts of the country, the Niger Delta imbroglio, and so on. However, the Boko haram group remains arguably Nigeria’s biggest security threat. The group poses a significant threat to neighbouring countries as well, especially Cameroon, Niger, and Chad resulting in grave economic, social, and humanitarian consequences. For example, the group gruesomely executed 40 rice farmers in Jere Local Government Area of Borno State, Nigeria. The United Nations had claimed that the number of death were far more than reported. But while the Group referred to as the armed bandits are increasingly making lives difficult for the people living in the Northwest area of Nigeria. Life is no longer sacred in these parts of the country and the overall impact will certainly last for generations. Government is clearly overwhelmed and the citizens helpless. It is therefore, expedient to examine the dynamics of this recent surge in armed banditry, the challenges inhibiting the fight against banditry and how to prevent the total shutdown of the country by bandits and insurgents alike. But first, who are these bandits? Bandit’s violence is not a new phenomenon in Nigeria. The history of banditry in Nigeria can be traced to pre-civil war period when government deteriorated in certain parts of the old Western region resulting in political violence, crime and organized insurgency. Accordingly, during the civilian

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reign, local bandits were reportedly stealing domestic animals. Recently, in North west area of Nigeria particularly in Zamfara, Sokoto, Katsina, Niger, Kaduna and Sokoto States, the activities of bandits have been particularly worrisome. Their modus operandi involves maiming and killing their victims when they least expect. Usually, they mobilized themselves through the forests into the neighbourhood riding on fast motorcycles especially in the nights and shoots at will. Sometimes in the afternoon, once they were sure there were no security presences of the police or military around; they unleash terror in the communities. This growing threat is claiming victims in hundreds. Several children have been orphaned and women became widows overnight while the issue of food security as well as humanitarian tragedy will further make life unbearable for many Nigerians.

CATTLE RUTLINGS

Cattle rustlings have become a major crime in Nigeria recently, with the northern region being the hardest hit. In the past few years, cattle rustling is a theft of a huge number of cows, deaths of people and destruction of property. Daily reports across the northern region have confirmed that cattle rustling have significantly contributed to the increasing security challenges facing the Nigeria state and seem to have become big business involving the Herders, big time syndicate, and heavy armed bandits. However, despite the growing level of cattle rustling and its consequences for society, the situation has yet to receive adequate scholarly interrogation.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Suleiman, Iguda , Bilkisu, Matawali, (2020) posit that in Nigeria, banditry came as a result of nearly four decades of unresolved conflicts between settled cultivators and nomadic herding communities that wander on the high plains of the northern Nigeria particularly the North west geo-political zone in states such as Zamfara. Katsina Sokoto, Kaduna, Birnin Kebbi ,and Niger. Banditry in Zamfara state since around 2009 and increased in 2009 and increase in 2011 especially after the general elections (Anka, 2017). In fact, Zamfara state has been the epicentre of banditry in Nigeria, where most of the bandits' leaders were based and from Zamfara state forest they would move riding on motor cycles to the other states such as Katsina, Niger, Kaduna, Birnin Kebbi and Sokoto, to operate and return to their forest dens (Farooq and Chukwu, 2020).

Therefore, by the year 2010, banditry had started in Katsina state that shared boundary with Zamfara, Birnin Kebbi state namely Jibia, Batsari, Safana, Danmusa, Kankara, Faskari and Sabua. Since banditry involved acts of robbery and violence on the people particularly rural dwellers who mainly engaged in farming, cattle rearing and other food production activities, it is bound to have the world Food summit in 1996 exist when all people at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active healthy life” (FAO, 2008). The food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2010) simply defines food security as the available of food in terms of production, distribution and consumption. Any form of violence that lead to insecurity in rural areas where majority of the people are farmers is bound to affect food security anywhere in the world. The United Nations in September 2020 observed that attacks by Al-Shabaab insurgent group will deepen food insecurity into the year 2021 in Mozambique (channels, 2020). In Nigeria, the federal government has realized that banditry has posed a serious threat to farming communities in the northern part of country

. Research Hypotheses

1. That Fulani who are less educated are perceived to be armed bandits than the educated ones.
2. Fulani people whose cattle have been rustled are perceived to be more likely to be armed bandits.
3. That Fulani people whose family are killed by vigilante groups are perceived to be Armed bandits.

Research Questions

1. What are the causes of armed banditry in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria?
2. What is the extent of armed banditry in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria?
3. What are the consequences of armed banditry in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria?
4. How does education/Religious attainment influence Armed banditry in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria?
5. What will be the possible solution to armed banditry in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria?

Aims and Objective

The general aim of this study is to examine the factors that influence Armed Banditry. This aim will be pursued through the following objectives

1. To investigate the causes / nature of armed banditry in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria
2. To ascertain the extent of banditry in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria.
3. To determine the consequences of banditry on the economic, and social development of Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria.
4. To identify how education/Religious attainment influence Armed banditry
5. To proffer solutions to armed banditry in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study has both theoretical and practical significance. Theoretically, the study will add to the body of existing knowledge on the factors influencing banditry generally kidnapping in Birnin Kebbi Nigeria in particular. It will be a source of resource material for future researchers in this area. The findings of the study will be useful to policy makers, other agencies, stakeholders on Armed banditry, Kidnapping, Armed robbery and organizations that are concerned with banditry in Nigeria and Birnin Kebbi in particular and beyond. The study will further show how improved peaceful co-existence will hasten the pace of economic activities in the area.

Scope of the study

The scope of the research study is limited to Birnin Kebbi State

Issues and trend of banditry and the dilemma of human security in Birnin kebbi, Nigeria

Ahmed, (2013) observed that the deteriorating situation of human security in Nigeria account for the increasing incidents of rural banditry and cattle rustling. 'Human security' is much bordered than national security, which tends to focus on the security of the state in military terms, and the protection of the state from external aggression. Human security shares the conceptual space of the people-centric approach to human development pioneered by the United Nations development programme (UNDP, 1994). Central to the idea of human security, as espoused by 1994 human development report on human security are two important concerns: freedom from fear intended to indicate freedom from violence and freedom from want, which is intended to indicate freedom from poverty (Greiner, 2013).

In this concept of human security, human being becomes the ‘vital core’, with a ‘fundamental set of function related to survival, livelihood and dignity’ as the irreducible minimum. The multidimensional nature of human security is underlined by the recognition given to economic, food, health, environmental, personal, community, and political security. The number of central issues is greatly expended, to include the welfare of citizens, larger issues of development, and redistribution of wealth among the different strata of society (fabusoro, 2007). There is also concern given to issues of governance the realization of social citizenship for social group and classes, and respect for group identity and self-determination of minority groups. The key assumption is that a nation cannot be secured if it fails to address issues of governance, unemployment, and corruption, all of which can subvert the rule of law and can undermine the welfare of the citizenry, even if the state has most modernized army or the most sophisticated police force (Fiki & Lee 2004). The human security situation in Nigeria has remained precarious despite the result of the 2013 rebasing of the Nigeria economy, which identified the country as having the 28 largest economies in the world and the largest in Africa.

IMPACTS OF BANDITRY ON FOOD SECURITY IN BIRNIN KEBBI, NIGERIA

Suleiman, Bilkisu and Matawalli (2020) postulated six impacts of armed banditry in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria which includes:

Chasing farmers out of their farms

Bandits chased farmers out of their farms when they see them working there. As the bandits are well armed, they ran after the farmers on their motorcycle with the intention to hurt or kill and the farmer had no option than to run since the farmers are not armed. In certain instances it was the sound of gun shots coming from the forest or sound of gun shot in the air that chased farmers out of their farmlands.

Seizing of farmland

This occurs where farmlands are located very close to the forest hideout of the bandits. It also occurs outside villages that have been completely deserted due to incessant attacks by the bandits. The bandits seized the farmlands and use them as grazing fields for the large number of cattle they acquired illegally through cattle rustling activities. In some areas where the bandits have not seized the farmlands, the bandits drive their cattle into the farmlands to eat up crops that have started to germinate after the first rains were recorded.

Review of Relevant Theories

Theorist of Armed Banditry

Thomas Hobbes (1679) was an English philosopher, considered to be one of the founders of modern political philosophy. Hobbes is best known for his 1651 book *Leviathan*, in which he expounds an influential formulation of social contract theory. In addition to political philosophy, Hobbes contributed to a diverse array of other fields, including history, jurisprudence, geometry, the physics of gases, theology, and ethics, as well as philosophy in general

ROUTINE ACTIVITY THEORY

The routine activities theory (RAT) was pioneered by Cohen and Felson (1979) in an attempt “to understand patterns and upward trend of predatory criminal events in the historical context of changing economy” (Hsieh and Wang 2018). The theory holds that crime is likely to occur when there is a spatial-temporal convergence of three essential elements of crime, namely a motivated offender, an attractive target, and the absence of capable guardianship. According to exponents of the theory (Cohen and Felson 1979, Maxfield 1987 Samson 2013), motivated offenders are individual who are capable and willing to commit a crime while suitable targets can be a person or object that are considered by offenders as venerable or attractive. On the other hand, guardianship can be a person or an object that is effective in deterring offense to occur. Mere physical presence of guardianship in space and time can deter crime committal. The routine activity theory is based on some basic assumption (Cohen and Felson 1979; Garofalo 1987; Maxfield 1987; Felson and Cohen 1980):

- Crime is likely to occur when there is a spatial-temporal convergence of three essential elements of crime, namely a motivated offender, an attractive target, and the absence of capable guardianship;
- The factors that render a particular target attractive are situational and crime-specific;
- Crime can be perpetrated by anyone who has the opportunity in terms of capability and availability of vulnerable target;
- Victims have choice on whether to be victims mainly by possibly avoiding situation where a crime can be committed against them;

THE REVISIONIST THEORY

The revisionist theory of national arose in a dialectical opposition to the classical or traditional approach to national security. It was largely informed by the dynamics of the new world order and the corresponding security threats thereof. The theory is characterized by its people-centred focus, multi-disciplinary posture and radical stance (Usman, 2012). Applied to the purpose of the present discourse, it is to be observed that rural banditry is a crime that has been precipitated and sustainable by the prevailing socio-existential environment in the rural sector characterized by a high proclivity to criminal indulgence. In the case of focal area, north-western Nigeria, the presence and prevalence of under-police and unregulated hinterlands, forestlands and borderlands have provided an enormous opportunity for rural criminality. In addition, the viable but vulnerable rural economy based largely on animal husbandry, crop production and informal mining, equally provides an avalanche of handy crime object /target: cattle, cash, treasure, etc. in the context, the virtue absence of governmental security apparatus in most rural communities gives incentive for criminal opportunity and impunity as well(the humanitarian 2018). In all, the aforementioned ecology of crime brings about, not only motivation but also temptation, for criminal indulgence. Under the circumstance, criminal deterrence takes flight all forms of predatory crime prevail. This is typically the situation in northern Nigeria, where rural marauders and brigands are having a sustained field day in a criminal escaped that is threatening to overrun the entire region. (Al-Chukwuma and kpaeke) (2014)

PATTERNS OF RURAL BANDITRY IN BIRNIN KEBBI NIGERIA

The authors further argued that four patters of rural banditry will be discussed in this study, namely village raids, highway robbery, kidnapping and cattle rustling. Village raids are the invasion and plundering of rural communities, especially at nights. These often take the form of scorch-earth attacks that leave affected communities in utter desolation in the aftermath of an incident. Village raids can be uni-episodic or coordinated. The former occurs when a single community is attacked while the latter happens when the attack occurs simultaneously on a number of adjacent communities within a locality. The principle purpose of village raids is material plundering. In effect,

in most instances, household, farmland, that some of the attack have been merely reprisals, designed to show down on the communities, which have hitherto challenge or resisted the bandits' onslaught through organized vigilantism.(Okoli 2017). Village raids have been a common feature of rural banditry escapade in north- kebbi state, Nigeria. .

METHODOLOGY

The methodology that was adopted to collect data for the study is field visit to the state and their villages mostly affected by armed bandits where banditry is endemic in kebbi state. The Villages that are seriously affected in kebbi state, are

The study posits that the roots of these new forms of violence and insecurity can be found in social, cultural, security, rule of law and democratic governance, which are so vital for political pluralism in Nigeria. It is the understanding of these new tendencies and their relative importance, amidst challenge of globalization, which is central to any research on violence, conflict and resolution in kebbi state, Nigeria.

Joshia (2015) maintains that the socio economic and political impact of banditry and cattle rustling are as follows;

SUFFERING, ESPECIALLY BY WOMEN

Cattle rustling and banditry have led to loss of many human lives and the displacement of various population groups. Women and children seem to bear the brunt in these new forms of violence. Contrary to traditional norms, they are not spared. Today women constitute 80% of the displaced and refugees in Africa. Violations of the fundamental rights of women and girls are widespread in times of war and civil strife, including atrocious crimes as well as rape, torture, murder, maltreatment and neglect.

BREAKDOWN OF THE SOCIAL ORDER

The target of non-combatants, especially women and children, seems to be symptoms of the breakdown of the entire social order. Another symptom is the way in which cattle are raided for selfish purposes. The pastoral communities have a lot of attachment to cattle due to their ritualistic and cultural importance. Thus, the loss of livestock is assumed to affect the entire social fabric.

ECONOMIC HARDSHIP

The 1980s happened to be a period characterized by drought and famines. At the same time the cattle-rustling menace appeared on the scene, bringing about a massive looting of livestock and destruction of property. The pokot and the turkana lost more than 80% of their livestock during this period. By February 1982 about 50% of the turkana population were in refugee camps and depended on relief supplies (Markakis 1993). Consequently, most people were in a state of despair, hoping for a “messiah” to deliver them from their unending tribulations. In most parts of Birnin kebbi, Nigeria it is extremely difficult for the pastoralists to get started again after heavy stock losses. Thus, social and economic differentiation is becoming more pronounced. As door boss asserts, “At present, class formation is incipient rather than existent and pastoralist by and large still make up a moral community of shared suffering rather than one divided by hereditary inequalities” (Markakis 1993). Very often the displaced and impoverished pastoralists have been forced to resort to selling firewood and charcoal or offering farm labour, which are regarded as degrading to the pastoral groups. As (Salih 1992) notes, “with no options of survival they have little choice but to exploit key environmental resources to provide food and income for survival”.

AN ENVIROMENT OF INSECURITY

Violence and warfare in kebbi State, Nigeria have created an environment of insecurity. Cattle rustling have created tension and conflict among the neighbouring societies. The twin phenomena of banditry and cattle rustling have become endemic in the region, affecting approximately two million people, ranging from the turkana in the north, the samburu and pokot in the centre, and the keiyo, marakwet and tugen in the south of the study area. The intensity of cattle rustling centred around the turkana, pokot and marakwet communities. Cattle warlords are having a field day in this environment of lawlessness. The idle and impoverished youths are easily manipulated by the warlord to join their private armies. The ability of the warlord to organize and arm their forces is a clear indication that the state no longer has the monopoly of the use of force. The pokot youth seems to be happy in enlisting into these armies, which they feel, is synonymous to depending societal interest against enemy, the state.

THE SHELVING OF DEVELOPMENT PROJECT

Because of the state of anarchy and lawlessness in the region it is very difficult to implement any development project. Government project. Government officers and the NGOs based in the area live in constant fear of the bandits. The often wanton destruction of life and property and the use of terror in all its manifestations tend to undermine the sense of value, dignity and harmony. It should be noted that a climate of peace is a prerequisite for the respect and enjoyment of human rights, and for sustainable socio-economic development. Kebbi State is no exception of this rule.

Theoretical Framework

No one theory can perfectly explain every aspect of crime or sources of armed banditry in Nigeria, and Kebbi State in particular. The need to incorporate various theories for better explanation cannot be overemphasised.

Expected Results

1. There might be significance relationship between people who perceived illiteracy to be involved in armed banditry in Kebbi State.
2. There might be a significant relationship between people who perceived Fulani people whose cattle has being rustled to be involved in armed banditry in Kebbi State.
3. There is significant difference between people who perceived Fulani people who are Moslems to be involved in armed banditry than their counterpart, Christians

Research Design

Design of the study

The study design appropriate for the study is a cross-sectional survey design. The reason for this research design is that it focuses on collection of data from large population at the same point in time using sample population (Babbie, 2007; Obasi, 1999). The researcher chose this research design method from the sample drawn to represent the various elements of the population generalize from the population of the study

Sample Size

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It will be a near impossible task to use the entire population of the State for this study. Consequently, a sample of 600 respondents will be used. Nwana (1981) assert that a well selected small sample could be more representative than a bigger one haphazardly selected. Therefore, a sample size will be statistically determined using “Taro Yamane” formula for a finite population. The formula is given as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where

n = sample size

N = the finite population

e = level of significance (or limit of tolerance error)

l = unity (a constant)

The total population of the state is put at people.

A sample size of 95 males 95 females from each of the LGA will be selected for the study i.e. 60+ 60= 120 x 5LGAs = 600 for the five LGAs. Based on the above population, 500 respondents will respond to the questionnaire, while 100 will be used for in-depth interview making a total sample of 600.

Sampling Technique

Multi-Stage Cluster sampling will be adopted for this study. According to Obasi (1999) cluster or area sampling involves selecting members of a sample in groups rather than individuals. The members of the target population may be grouped on the basis of occupation, region, religion or any common features

Shared by the group. A cluster sampling technique is usually used to select the sample from the identified clusters. Cluster sampling is suitable when the target population is too large and by implication, minimizes the costs that would have been spent on covering large sample.

At the first stage of the sampling, the first cluster comprises of five towns in each of the local governments, which will be randomly selected in each of the five local government areas, using simple random sampling (hand picking). In doing this, the number of towns in each local government will be written down in different pieces of paper and put inside a bag. The bag will be shaken very well after which one of the research assistants will be blindfolded and make to pick two pieces of paper from the

bag. The towns written in the selected pieces of paper will be sampled. In doing so, a total of five towns will be selected to form the first cluster.

In the second stage of the sampling, systematic random sampling will be used, in selecting eight villages from each of the towns in the first cluster. This will involve the researcher to have a list of all the villages in each town, which will act as the sampling frame at this stage. The total number of the villages will be divided by eight, which will be the sample of interest at this level in order to obtain the K^{th} element (interval size). After this, one number will be randomly chosen as a starting point while each ward that falls at the interval will be selected. As a result, the second stage will which consist of forty eight villages, which will be systematically selected from the six towns earlier selected from the five local government areas.

In the third stage, six household units will be selected from each of the wards using systematic random sampling; as a result, the total number of household units in each of the selected wards will be individually divided into six to get the interval size, after which one household will be randomly chosen as a starting point and other household at the subsequent interval selected for the study. However, in situations where any household refuses to participate in the study, such household will be replaced by the nearest household in the frame. As a result a total of two hundred and eighty eight households will be selected for the study.

In each household unit, two respondents will be selected (male and female) using systematic random sampling. However, the respondents must not be less than eighteen years of age in order to qualify to participate in the study.

In selecting respondents for the qualitative study, a total of one hundred key informants will be interviewed who must be either a Chief, Pastor, Imam, Opinion Leader, Chairman/ Chairperson, Councillor, Community Leader or Village Head, hence purposive sampling will be used in this regard, having allocated a quota sampling of twenty key informants per local government area. Such selection will be concentrated on the towns that make up the first cluster, thus, five key informants in every town.

Instruments for Data Collection

The study applied both quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection. Two instruments will be used for data collection in this study. These are: the questionnaire and in-depth interview (IDI) guide. The instruments are prepared in English but will be translated into Fulani/Hausa, to respondents by the research assistants. The questionnaire will contain both open-ended and close-ended questions and will be used to elicit information from the 500 respondents, and had two sections. Section A contains information on the characteristics of respondents such as age, sex, education, location, marital status, occupation, and family size. Section B contains information on Public perception on the factors influencing Armed Banditry in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

A total of 500 questionnaires will be administered to respondents in the study areas by the researcher and the assistants, while 100 will be used for interview by the researcher himself with the help of field assistants for three weeks. In-depth interview will be used to seek information from the key informants on the Factors influencing Armed banditry in Kebbi State, Nigeria

STUDY AREAS

Kebbi State

Is a (Hausa: Jihae Kebbi; Fulfulde: Leydi Kebbi) is a state that is bordered with Sokoto to the east and Zamfara to the north and to the south by Niger state, while its western border forms part of the national borders with Benin Republic and has 103 km (64 miles) and Niger 207 km (129 miles). Named for the city of Birnin Kebbi the state's capital and largest city. Of the 36 states of Nigeria, Kebbi is the tenth largest in area and 22nd most populous, with an estimated population of about 4.4 million as of 2016. The state is known as land of equity. Kebbi State was created out of the former Sokoto state on 17 August 1991, it has 21 Local government areas. The state has Sudan and Sahel-Savannah. Kebbi state has four emirate councils (Gwandu, Argungu, Yawuri and Zuru). The main ethnic groups are Hausa Fulani, Dakarkari, Kambarawa, Kungawa and Harmful

of Zabarmawa. Some of the towns/Villages attack by armed bandits are Koro, Kimpi, Gaya, Dimi, Zutu, Rafin gora and Iguende.

Study Population and Scope

The population of these communities is put at 1,440,824 people by Projection using United Nations for Developing Countries which is census population, which include male and female, married and unmarried, within the range of eighteen years and above. The population include occupations like farming (both in crop and animal husbandry), civil servants and traders. The population further includes adherents of Islam, Christianity and a few who practice traditional religion and all levels of education. In terms of scope, this study is limited to kebbi State and ethno-religious crises as they affect them

Physical Setting

Some of the local government mostly attacked by armed bandits are as follows Sakaba, Donka/Wasugu, Fakai Yawuri, and Bunza.

Wasugu/Dankomaga

Is a local government Area in Kebbi State, Nigeria. Its Headquarters is in the town of Ribah. It has an estimated population of 453,200(2022) projection Nigeria.

Yawuri (yauri)

is an emirate in Nigerians Kebbi state. It is one of the 21 Local Governments in Kebbi State occupying the yawuri Local Government Area. Today Yawuri is one of the smallest historical emirate in Kebbi state Nigeria. The estimated population of yawuri is 112,000.

Sakaba

Is a local Government Area under Zuru emirate in Kebbi state, Nigeria. Its headquarters are in the town of Dirindaji and has many Tribes, its has an estimated population of 89,937 at the census.2006

Fakai

Is a local government area in kebbi state. Its headquarters are in the town of mahuta. It has an area of 224,700 km² and estimated population of 121,212 people. Majority of the people are farmers, artisans, hunters and some few civil servants

Bunza

Is a local government area in kebbi state, Nigeria. Its headquarters are in the town of Bunza and was created in 1975 out of the then-state of Sokoto during the local

government reform under General Murtala Mohammed. It has an estimated population of 523,312.

The study will apply both quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection. Two instruments will be used for data collection in this study. These are: the questionnaire and in-depth interview guide IDI (In-depth-interview). The instruments will be prepared in English but will be translated into Hausa,/Fulani to respondents by the research assistants. The questionnaire will contain both open-ended and close-ended questions and will be used to elicit information from the 500 respondents, and has two section, while the in depth interview is an oral questionnaire .It is face to face interaction situation in which one person (interviewer) asks another person (interviewee) questions which are responded to orally . Section A contains information on the characteristics of respondents such as age, sex, education, location, marital status, occupation, and family size. Section B contains information on the factors influencing armed banditry in north-western Nigeria

Methods of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and percentages will be employed to determine the characteristics and distribution of each of the parameters found in the questionnaire using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). Information on these categories will be illustrated with pie-chart, bar graphs and line graphs. Parametric test (chi-square test (χ^2)) will be used to test the hypotheses of the study. Logistic Regression Analysis (LRA) will be used to predict the influence of dependent variables on independent variable e.g. Perception and Armed Banditry. The data from the in-depth interview will be edited and transcribed into codes. Quotes and expressions gathered will be identified and organized under distinct themes. In essence, the thematic method will be used in analysing the data gathered from the in-depth interview. In view of this, each theme shall be discussed and illustrative quotes pulled out to support and elucidate the quantitative data.

Administration of instruments

For easy collection of data, the researcher will recruit 4 field assistants comprising of 2 males and 2 females, 1 male and 1 female for the state. The reason for this number was to ensure that the research assistants are effectively managed in terms of funding, training,

supervision and time management. In the case of female respondents, female research assistants will be more useful, due to the sensitive nature of the study area, for instance, the Fulani would not allow a male assistant to enter his house. They will be trained by the researcher, who will also supervise the administration and collection of the questionnaires. The questionnaires will be self-administered. However, where the researcher/assistants find out that the respondent cannot read and write properly, only then will it be other-administered. The respondents selected for interview will be informed before time, as this will create conducive environment for the interview. The distribution of questionnaires and collection alongside in-depth interview will be done on weekdays, the time is in the evening 4.00pm – 6.00pm, and because that was the respondent’s leisure time (when people sit under the tree to rest). The male respondents will be located at “IDP camps “Majalisa”. Where people of the same calibre, ideology and thinking stay to rest while the female respondents will be located at their various households and it will last for three weeks

DATA ANALYSES

1. Name of L G A

- 2. (a) Sakaba ()
- (b) Donka/Wasagu ()
- (c) Yawuri ()
- (d) Fakai ()
- (e) Bunza ()

Sakaba	210	42
Donka/Wasagu	56	11.2
Yawuri	93	18.6
Fakai	74	14.8
Bunza	67	13.4
TOTAL	500	100

Table 1: Revealed that the number of local government affected banditry Sakaba is 42%, Donga/Wasugu 11.2%, Yawuri 18.6, Fakai 14.8%, Bunza 13.4%

Name of Towns/Villages

Name of Towns/villges	Frequency	Percentage %
Koro	30	6
Kipi	82	16.4
Gaya	79	15.8
Rafin gora	109	21.8
zutu	200	40
TOTAL	500	100%

Table 2: Revealed the number of tows/villages seriously affected by banditry, koro has 6%, Kipi has 16.4%, Gaya has 15.8%, Rafin gora has 21.8 and Zutu has 40%.respectively.

2 Sex: (a) Male []

(b) Female []

Sex	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	250	50%
Female	250	50%
TOTAL	500	100%

Table 2: Revealed the sex of respondents, Male has 50% and Female has 50%. This shows that the number of male equals the number of female.

3 Age group of respondents

- (a) 18 – 25 []
- (b) 25 – 35 []
- (c) 35 – 45 []
- (d) 45 – 55) []
- (e) 55 – 60 and above []

Age group (year)	Frequency	Percentage %
18-25	56	11.2%
25-35	93	18.6%
35-45	210	42%
45-55	74	14.8%
55-60 and above	67	13.4%
TOTAL	500	100%

Table 3. Revealed the age group of respondents; 18-25 is 11.2% majority of the respondents are within the age group of 35-45 years is 42% followed by those within the age group of 25-35 years 18.6%, While, 45-55%. Has 14.8% while 55-60 and above has

13.4% respectively, the above

4.. Marital status:

- (a) Single []
- (b) Married []
- (c) Divorced []
- (d) Widowed []
- (e) Separated []

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage %
Single	93	18.6%
Married	146	29.2 %
Divorced	126	25.2%
Widowed	80	16%
Separated	55	11%
TOTAL	500	100%

Table 4: The above table revealed the marital Status of respondents,Single has 18.6 Married has 29.2%, Divorced has 25.2%, , Widowed has 16%, and Separated has 11% respectively.

5.Ethnic Background

- (a) Hausa []
- (b) Fulani []
- (c) Dakarkari []
- (d) Kambawa ()
- (e) Kungawa/Zabamawa []

Ethnic Background	Frequency	Percentage %
Hausa	120	24
Fulani	33	6.6
Dakarkari	92	18.4
Kambaawa	64	12.8
Kumgawa/Zabamawa	191	38.2
TOTAL	500	100%

Table 5 : The table above revealed that the ethnic background of various tribes in the study areas, Fulani has 6.6, Hausa has 24%, Dakarkari has 18.4%, kambarawa has 12.8% and Kumgawa and Zabarmawa has 38.2% % Respectively.

6. . Occupational Background

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- (a) Artisan []
- (b) Civil Servant[]
- (c) Business []
- (d) Farmers []
- (e) Applicant []
- (f) Students []

Occupational Background	Frequency	Percentage%
Artisan	46	9.2
Civil Servant	37	7.4
Business	84	16.8
Farmers	216	43.2
Applicant	107	21.4
Students	10	2
TOTAL	500	100%

Table 6. Revealed the occupational Background of respondents in the following order: Farmers has 43.2%, Artisans has 9.2%, Civil Servants has 7.4%, Students has 2% ,Business has 16.8%, While Applicants represent 21.4%,.the Chart of the respondents based on occupational background below.

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7. LEVEL OF EDUCATION

(a) Non Formal Education []

Primary Education (b) []

(c) Secondary Education []

(d) Tertiary Education []

LEVEL OF EDUCATION.

Level of Education	Frequency	Percentage %
Non Formal Education	222	44.4
Primary Education	25	5
Secondary Education	63	12.6
Tertiary Education	190	38
TOTAL	500	100%

Table 7 :The table above revealed the level of Education, Non-Formal Education has 44.4%, Primary education has 5%, Secondary education has 12.6%, and Tertiary has 38, respectively.

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8. What is your religious affiliation?

- (a) Islam []
- (b) Christianity []
- (c) African Traditional Religion []
- (d) Others,

TABLE 8. RELIGIOUS AFFILIATION.

What is your religious	Frequency	Percentage%
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affiliation		
Islam	184	36.8
Christianity	82	16.4
African Traditional Religion	69	13.8
Others	165	33
Total	500	100%

Table 8: Revealed that Islam has 36.8%, Christians has 16.4% and African traditional Religion has 13.8% Others has 33% Hence the number of Moslems outnumbered that of Christians and ATR.

SECTION B: SOCIO-CULTURAL FACTORS INFLUENCING CONFLICT

Instruction: Please tick (√) as applicable.

9. What is the extent of Banditry between Fulani/Hausa,/Others in your town and Villages in your State ?

(a) []

(b) []

(c) e []

(d)

Response option	Frequency	Percentage
It is very serious	45	9
It has been for a long time	231	46.2
It is destructive in nature	98	19.6
It has sent people away from their homes	126	25.2
TOTAL	500	100%

Figure 1

Table 9. Revealed that 42% of the respondents argued that it is very serious and killing, others argued that it has been for a long time, and has 19.2% and ,it is destructive in nature, and has 34% and lastly it has sent people away from their homes and has 4.8% respectively.

10. What are the factors that necessitated Banditry among Hausa/Fulani and others in your State? (Please tick as many as applicable to you)

- (a) Boundary issues []
- (b) Indigene/settler dichotomy []
- (c) Chieftaincy Tussle []
- (d) Grazing land issue []
- (e) Unemployment, []
- (f) One’s beliefs and attitudes []
- (g) Poor orientation on traditional values and norms []
- (h) Others (specify)

Response Option	Frequency	Percentage
Boundary issues	20	4
Indigene/settler dichotomy	30	6
Chieftancy Tussle	65	13
Unemployment	106	21.2
Ones beliefs and attitudes	66	13.2
Poor orientation on traditions values and norms	86	17.2
Other specify	32	6.4
Grazing land issue	95	19
Total	500	100%

Table 10. revealed that one of the causes of banditry in their state is boundary issue which has 4%,and others argued that indigene issue as one of the cause of banditry and it has 6% chieftaincy tussle has 13%, while Grazing land issues has 19% Unemployment has the highest figure of 21.2%and ones belief and attitude has 13.2% poor orientation on values has 17.2% and lastly others has 6.4% respectively.

11. Have you ever being a victim of kidnapping in your town/village?

If yes, please give your experience

Response option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	220	44
No	280	56
Total	500	100%

Table 11: Revealed that 44% of the respondent said they have once being victim of kidnapping and only 56% did not witness the killing/kidnapping.

12. Is the killing /kidnapping justified

Response option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	499	99.8
No	1	0.2
TOTAL	500	100%

Table 12. Revealed that 99.8 % of the respondent said they are justified, while 0.2 % said there is no justification in killing people and rustling of their domestic cattle, burning of their houses.

13. How does Armed Banditry affect the economic and social development of your Town/Village/State, (Please tick as many as applicable to you)

- (a) House breaking []
- (b) Ethnic strife []
- (c) Stagnation of business activities []
- (d) Low agricultural output and investment []
- (f) Water scarcity []
- (g) Others (specify)

Response option	Frequency	Percentage
House Breaking	36	7.2
Ethnic strife	55	11
Stagnation of business activities	23	4.6
Low agricultural output and investment	56	11.2

investment		
Water supply	243	48.6%
Other specify	87	17.4
TOTAL	500	100%

Table: 14. Revealed how banditry affect the social and economic development of their states, some of the respondents argued that there is the issue of house breaking and it has 7.2% while others argued ethnic strife more especially between the Hausa Fulani communities, stagnation of business activities has 11% low agricultural output and investment which has the figure of 5.8% water scarcity has 56% and lastly others has 17.4%

15. What is your occupation before the crises ?

- (a) Farming []
- (b) Artisan []
- (c) Civil Servant []
- (d) Student []
- (e) Business []
- (f) Others (specify)

Response option	Frequency	Percentage
Farming	216	43.2
Artisan	37	7.4
Civil Servant	107	21.4
Student	84	16.8
Business	46	9.2
Others Specify	10	2
TOTAL	500	100%

Table 15. Revealed the occupation of respondents at time of attack, Farming which represent 43.2% was the major occupation of the respondents, Artisan has 7.4%, civil

servants has 21.4%, Students has 16.8%, business has 9.2%, and others such as applicant has 2%. Respectively.

16. What is your present occupation

- (a) Farming []
- (b) Artisan []
- (c) Civil Servant []
- (d) Student []
- (e) Business []
- (f) Others []

Response option	Frequency	Percentage
Farming	200	40
Artisan	124	24.8
Civil Servant	96	19.2
Student	19	3.8
Business	40	0.84
Others Specify	21	8.8
TOTAL	500	100%

Table 16. Revealed that 40% of the respondents still engaged in farming. While artisan has 24.8% while civil servant 19.2% . Students has 3.8%. Business has 0.84%, and others has 8.8%

17. Did you change location after any of the attack ?

- (a) Yes []
- (b) No []

Response option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	440	88%
No	60	12%
TOTAL	500	100%

Table 17. Revealed that 88% of the respondents changed location after most of the attacks, and 12% of the respondents did not change location.

Response option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	369	73.8%
No	131	26.2%
TOTAL	500	100%

18. Where did you move to if yes

(a) To live with Relatives []

(b) To live with Friends

(c) To live with people of the same faith []

Response option	Frequency ²	Percentage
To live with relatives	69	13.8
To live with friends	314	62.8
To live with people of the same faith	117	23.4
TOTAL	500	100%

Table 18. Revealed that 13.8% of the respondents lived with relatives during any attack, 62.8% lived with friends, while 23.4% of the respondents live with people of the same faith.

19. Banditry is higher in communities with low unemployment, do you agree?

(a) Yes []

(b) No []

Response option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	480	96
No	20	4%
TOTAL	500	100%

Table 19 : Revealed that 96% of the respondents perceived banditry as being higher in communities with cases of unemployment, while 4% of the respondents did not agree.

20. Persistent Fulani/Hausa and others, perceived kidnapping/killing of people as significantly related to government’s nonchalant attitude.

(a) Yes

(b) No

Response option	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	467	93.4
No	33	6.6
TOTAL	500	100

Table 20: Revealed that 93.4% of the respondents agreed that persistent killing in kebbi state as significantly related to governments nonchalant attitude, While 6.6% of the respondents were not of this option.

21. What are the possible solutions to these persistent killing/? (Please tick as many as applicable to you)

(a) Beefing security in all the affected LGAs

(b) To implement committee reports on conflicts

(c) Job creation

(d) Provision of basic amenities.

(e) Continuous and institutionalized dialogue among involved parties

(f) Government to educate the people to see themselves as brothers and sisters

(g) Government to have proper boundary demarcation

(h) To encourage communities to engage in re-orientation of norms/values

(i) Others (specify).....

.....

.....

Table 22

Response option	Frequency	Percentage
Beefing up security in all LGA’s	93	18.6
Non-implementation of committee reports on conflicts	55	11
Job Creation	200	40
Provision of basic amenities	38	7.6
Continues and institutionalized dialogue among parties	22	4.4
Government to educate the people to see themselves as brothers and sisters	76	15.2
To encourage communities to engaged in reorientation of norms/values	16	3.2
TOTAL	500	100%

Table 21. Revealed that the Responses the option of Beefing up security in all LGA’s in the affected areas in all the L. G s is 18.6%, Non-implementation of committee reports on conflicts is 11%, Job Creation is 40%, Provision of Basic amenities is 7.6%,

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Continues and institutionalized dialogue among parties is 4.4%, Government to Educate the people to see themselves as brothers and sisters is 15.2%, While To encourage communities to engage in reorientation of norms/values is 3.2% respectively.

EXPECTED RESULT

- 25. Hausa/Fulani people who are educated are perceived to be involved in banditry more than their counterparts who are not educated in the aforementioned States.
- 26 Males are perceived to be more significantly associated with banditry than females in the Aforementioned State
- 27. Fulani people whose cattle has been rustled are likely to participate in armed banditry more than those who are not in the aforementioned State.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1

Hausa/Fulani people who are educated are perceived to be involved in Armed Banditry more than their counterparts who are not educated.

Hausa/Fulani people who are educated are perceived not to be involved in armed banditry more than their counterparts who are not educated.

1. Table 25; Level of education and involvement in armed banditry.

To test this hypothesis, education was recorded too high and low. Low education include non formal education, primary and secondary education, while high education include tertiary education.

Involment in Armed Banditry

Level of Education	Yes	No	Total
High Education	99(29.8)	233(70.2)	332(100.0)
Low Education	132(55.5)	106(44.5)	238(100.0)
Total	231(40.5)	339(59.5)	570(100.0)

Critical value of $X^2=3.841$ @.05level of significant

Hypotheses 2

Males are perceived to be significantly associated with armed banditry more than females in the study areas.

Females are perceived not to be associated with armed banditry compare to their Males counterpart in the study areas

Table 26: contingency involving sex and involvement in armed banditry cross tabulation.

2. Involvement in Armed Banditry

Sex	Yes	No	Total
Male	203(67.7)	97(32.3)	300(100.0)
Female	87(29.0)	213(71.0)	300(100.0)
Total	290(48.3)	310(51.7)	600(100.0)

$x^2 = .390; df=1; 612$

Critical=3.841 @.05significant level

To test this hypotheses, table 2 is cross tabulated with involvement in banditry.

T

the critical value which is 3.841 is greater than the calculated value which is 0.378. therefore, we reject the research hypotheses and accept the null hypotheses which says that females are perceived not to be significantly associated with armed banditry compare to their female counterpart .

Hypotheses 3

Muslims are likely to participate in armed banditry

Moslems are not likely to participate in armed banditry more than Christians.

To test this hypotheses, Table 9. (Religious affiliation) is cross tabulated with Table 12. (involvement in banditry Table 27. Contingency table for religion and involvement in armed banditry cross tabulation.

Involvement in Armed Banditry

Religion	Yes	No	Total
Moslems	122(38.4)	196(62.6)	318(100.0)
Christians	11(21.9)	160(78.1)	205(100.0)
African Traditional Religion	5(74.5)	12(25.5)	47(100.0)
Total	202(35.4)	368(64.6)	570(100.0)

$x^2 = .378; df=2; p=.595$

Critical $x^2 = 53.991 @ .05$ significant level

Since the critical value of x which is 5.991 at .05 level of significant is greater than the calculated value which is 0.378, we accept the study hypotheses and conclude that Moslems are most likely to participate in banditry more than Christians in the five states affected

Calculated Chi-square value is 0.337 while the critical value is 3.841. Since the critical value is greater than the calculated value, we accept the null hypotheses of no relationship. In other words, education has influence in ones participation in banditry among Fulani/Hausa.

Discussion/Findings on unemployment/

On the Influence of socio-cultural factors that caused banditry among Fulani/Hausa in the affected areas. Table 19 shows that Grazing land dispute issue and unemployment was the most caused of banditry.

It was also found out that the greatest consequences of the banditry was stagnation of business activities, Low agricultural output and investment, and Social development.

Table 21. . In terms of possible solutions to these persistent conflicts,

Respondents agreed that Job creation, beefing of security in all the LGAs is the best possible solution to the persistent banditry in the study areas.

Re-occurrence of crises has also weakened the social relationship that existed among the people and caused mutual suspicion instead of cooperation among them.

The findings in Table 22. Revealed that unemployment issue was the most important factor (28 %) while those with moderate are Job Creation, beefing of security has lesser chances of engaging in banditry.

Data from In-depth interview (IDIs) with mall. Yaro a chief in Koro town revealed that the crises created inconveniences, it has reduced the standard of living of most families and further impoverished the already pauperized people of the study areas. Mall Abubakar village head in kipi town in revealed that some households which had better accommodation before the crises now have to live in substandard houses with little or no facilities. This is associated with the destruction during the attack and also limited resources to rehabilitate or develop new ones. However, mall..Ardo, a ward leader in Gaya town, revealed that what is found to be common is increase in construction of round hut types of houses which are least attractive but provide immediate solution to the accommodation problems of the time.

However, indepth interview data with mall shamsudeen an opinion leader in Rafin Gora town shows that more modern structures are springing up in all districts. Again, mall. Iro a chief in Zutu town revealed that, before the crises, the situation was a little different as mixed settlement was more common while residential segregation, though present, did not exist for any special reason. Most respondents claimed they were mixed settlements before the crises started while others identified segregated settlements due to socio-economic reasons. However, the bond among residents is weakened and both mixed settlements and segregated settlement sprang up. Many families had to relocate to other areas because of insecurity and fear of attacks. Among those who relocated, majority of them are living with kith and kin while others lived with people of the same faith.

The findings of the study on the extent of attack between the Fulani/Hausa in these study areas revealed that the crisis is usually very serious and destructive and has been on for a long time as shown in Table 9 and is 'supported by the views of some of those interviewed. For example, Mall.SamboAdamu an opinion leader in Dipi town ,Garba sani a Farmer in koro and Auwalu musa, an opinion leader also in Dipi town unanimously emphasized that Armed Banditry posed a serious problem to the community and was very destructive.

The findings of the study on the major factors responsible for this attacks revealed that Unemployment as the major cause of banditry in the affected states. Others argued that Boundary issues, grazing land issue, chieftaincy tussle , unemployment are the major factors responsible for the crises.

Hajia Aisha in Dimi town also confirm that all the above factors are responsible for the crises

Mall. Sarki Dauda an opinion leader in koro town stressed that banditry affects farming activities thereby causing low agricultural output and investment. Further stated that some hoodlums usually used the period to break into people's houses.

Finally, the findings of the study on possible solutions to these persisted attacks include beefing up security in all the LGAs, job creation, provision of basic amenities, continuous and institutionalised dialogue among involved parties, government to educate people to see themselves as brothers and sisters, government to have proper boundary demarcation, and to encourage communities to engage in re Orientation of norms and values. In support of the approve, Mall. Sani Abubakar, one of the ward leader in , Gaya stressed that having proper boundary demarcation and educating people to be united would ease the problem of banditry in their area. Some of the spiritual leaders interviewed, include mall. Alh. Lawan in Rafin gora town , and Adullahi Zamani, an imam in Zutu town suggested that more emphasis should be Placed on Job creation, and also continuous dialoguing with the warring bandits would solvé the problem of banditry in their area.

RECOMMENDATION

The findings throughout the study show that peace is indispensable to development and a prerequisite to the thriving of human activities. Based on these findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1 Government of kebbi State, Nigeria should build upon the existing, albeit, fragile peace and reconciliation efforts by promoting awareness campaigns ,through radio and other local media, that focus on commonalities rather than differences between ethnic groups.

2 It should develop an early warning and response mechanism in conjunction with the relevant security agencies.

3. Local Government, private individuals and communities should join hands to provide uninterrupted access of the masses to education, health services, employment and other physical development facilities for quality living.

4. Government should meet periodically to dialogue with youth leaders, community leaders, traditional rulers and religious leaders in the areas on issues that affects them, seek their advice and suggest where necessary. This will give everyone a sense of belonging and foster the spirit of brotherliness among warring communities. On land problems, government should promote all appropriate measures to maximize the allocation of land for purposes that are, not in the interest of peoples welfare.

5. The various groups should re-organize themselves into development groups such as trade unions, community development associations tribal unions, farm groups cooperative societies and even age grades. These groups should be registered and given a workable mode of operation and a constitution by the government which should charge them to identify their problems and how best to solve same and also assist them financially, morally and materially. By doing so, people will always think of developing themselves and their communities and the feeling of isolation from the scheme of things will be non-existent. This will avert communal conflicts in the area. The leaders of the various communities should meet periodically and discuss issues that affect their area and also see areas they could come together to curb crime, conflicts and other negative developments in their immediate environment...
6. Government to make a law anybody found with bandiry/kidnapping to face death sentence.

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